

Modeling of factors influencing football talent management at Mes Rafsanjan club based on AHP method

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Abstract

The main objective of this study was to identification of factors influencing football talent management in Mes Rafsanjan Club based on AHP method. The sample included 15 experts selected through purposive sampling. Pillips and Roper (2009) standard questionnaire through using experts' opinions and forming couple comparison Matrix between items was developed. To categorize and identity factors influencing talent management, Analytical Hierarchy Process was used. The Results showed that from expert views, "Talent attraction" factors had the most important factors influencing talent management with the value of 0/493. Considering the results and the importance of talent attraction in talent management at the Mes Rafsanjan club, it is necessary for the club's officials to develop a comprehensive plan to discover and attract athletic talent at this club.

Keywords: Talent management, Talent retention, Talent attraction, Mes Rafsanjan club, AHP

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